

1 **Transforming potential of the beta genus papillomavirus E6 and E7 oncoproteins.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 The beta genus and alpha genus papillomaviruses are primarily distinguished based on tissue-specific
7 tropism; the alpha genus infect the anogenital and oral mucosa while the beta genus infect the skin. The
8 transforming properties of high-risk alpha genus papillomaviruses types HPV18 and HPV16 are
9 understood as a function of their ability to result in cancer in the cervix; transforming potential of some
10 types in the beta genus is suspected but not fully understood, nor is it known how this compares to that of
11 the alpha genus high risk types. We measured total transcription in human cells following expressing of
12 the HPV early genes, oncogenes E6 and E7, which inactivate p53 and pRb, respectively, for the two most
13 prevalent high risk alpha genus types HPV16 and HPV18, as well as for the beta genus types HPV122,
14 HPV38b and HPV107, and measured induction of transformation. Each of the three beta genus HPV types
15 we studied here can be classified as high-risk, as expression of their E6/E7 proteins in human cells was
16 sufficient to result in transformation. Beta genus transformation was quantitatively equivalent between
17 types HPV107, HPV122 and HPV38b; transformation by the alpha genus HPV16 and HPV18 E6/E7
18 proteins was of slightly higher efficiency. The data together indicate the presence of papillomaviruses
19 outside of the alpha genus with clear transforming potential in human cells.
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Results

We measured total transcription in fibroblasts from the human skin following expression of the E6 and E7 oncogenes from three separate types of beta genus HPV types, to study in an unbiased fashion their transforming capacities: HPV38b, HPV122 and HPV107.

Figure 1: HPV38b has transforming potential.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1894	1.55E-01	0.359	-1.42362	-0.5116248	1651.92	ECT2	4320/16076	73.1

Figure 2: HPV122 has transforming potential.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1894	1.51E-01	0.38	-1.434259	-0.545012	1674.1	ECT2	3321/16060	79.3

Figure 3: HPV107 has transforming potential.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1894	2.49E-01	0.376	-1.1529484	-0.43347425	1605.25	ECT2	3564/16142	77.9

We also measured total transcription in fibroblasts from the human skin following expression of the E6 and E7 oncogenes from three separate types of alpha genus HPV types, to study in an unbiased fashion their transforming capacities: HPV16 and HPV18.

Figure 4: The transforming potential of high-risk alpha genus HPV16 and HPV18 is slightly higher than that of the beta genus HPV types HPV38b, HPV122 and HPV107.

Figure 4a: The E6/E7 oncoproteins of HPV16 are highly transforming.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1894	9.16e-04	0.366	-3.315155	-1.2143063	2136.17	ECT2	657/16219	95.9

Figure 4b: The E6/E7 oncoproteins of HPV18 are highly transforming.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1894	1.04e-03	0.349	-3.279996	-1.1446419	2128.83	ECT2	939/16348	94.3

Discussion

We demonstrated that the beta genus E6 and E7 early genes are oncoproteins and can function as *bona fide* oncogenes. Beta genus HPV types HPV38b, HPV107 and HPV122 have transforming potential.